

4. Звіт про результати аналізу ринків послуг термінації трафіка на мережах рухомого (мобільного) зв'язку від 20.10.2011 № 585 [Електронний ресурс]. – Режим доступу: <http://nkrz.gov.ua> – Заголовок з екрана.

5. **Енин, С. В.** Роль информационных технологий в инновационном развитии [Электронный ресурс] / С. В. Енин. – Режим доступа: http://www.vsel.by/File/2008_05/Enin.pdf. – Загл. с экрана.

6. **Бреус, С. В.** Аналіз інноваційної діяльності промислових підприємств в Україні [Текст] / С. В. Бреус // Актуальні пробл. економіки. – 2004. – №5. – С. 121–128.

7. **Кокурин, Д. И.** Инновационная деятельность [Текст] / Д. И. Кокурин. – М.: Экзамен, 2001. – 575 с.

8. Організація та здійснення інноваційної діяльності [Текст]: метод. вказівки. – К.: Укр. ІНТЕІ, 2007. – 208 с.

9. **Медынский, В. Г.** Инновационное предпринимательство [Текст]: учеб. пособие / В. Г. Медынский, Л. В. Скалюй. – М.: ЮНИТИ-ДАНА, 2002. – 589 с.

10. **Козловський, В. О.** Інноваційний менеджмент [Текст]: навч. посіб. / В. О. Козловський. – Вінниця: ВНТУ, 2007. – 210 с.

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PROBLEMS OF REFORMING THE LAW ENFORCEMENT SYSTEM OF THE STATE: AN INNOVATIVE METHOD OF MOTIVATION OF STAFF

The features of the restructuring process of the law enforcement system of Ukraine. The methods for creating an effective system of motivation of employees in structural change. Revealed more important areas of improving the motivation of social actors in the activities to achieve the strategic objectives in the fight against crime, ensure social security in the material and spiritual spheres of society. The ways of creating opportunities for implementation of the individual abilities of employees, providing depth study of individual abilities and needs of each individual artist to intensify its efforts to achieve the goals of the organization. Explore such ways to encourage employees of law-enforcement sphere, as participation in development and decision-making, the introduction of competitive vacant posts, the demilitarization of special ranks, the democratization of the personnel policy, the development of professional mobility of employees.

Key words: motivation, innovation, promotion, management, reform the law enforcement sphere, the police, personnel, international experience and European standards, international experts.

Проаналізовано особливості процесу перебудови правоохоронної системи України. Досліджено способи створення ефективної системи мотивації працівників під час структурних перетворень. Виявлено найважливіші напрями вдосконалення процесу спонукання соціальних суб'єктів до діяльності з досягнення стратегічних цілей у боротьбі зі злочинністю, забезпечення соціальної безпеки в матеріальній і духовній сферах суспільства. Розглянуто способи реалізації індивідуальних здібностей співробітників, що передбачають ґрунтовне вивчення індивідуальних здібностей і потреб кожного окремого виконавця для активізації його діяльності з досягнення цілей організації. Досліджено такі шляхи стимулювання співробітників правоохоронної сфери,

як участь у розробці та прийнятті рішень, запровадження конкурсного займання вакантних посад, демілітаризація спеціальних звань, демократизація кадрової політики, розвиток професійної мобільності службовців.

Ключові слова: мотивація, інновації, стимулювання, керування, реформування, правоохоронна сфера, поліція, кадрова політика, міжнародний досвід, європейські стандарти, міжнародні експерти.

Проанализированы особенности процесса перестройки правоохранительной системы Украины. Исследованы способы создания эффективной системы мотивации работников при структурных преобразованиях. Выявлены наиболее важные направления совершенствования процесса побуждения социальных субъектов к деятельности по достижению стратегических целей в борьбе с преступностью, обеспечению социальной безопасности в материальной и духовной сферах общества. Рассмотрены способы реализации индивидуальных способностей сотрудников, предусматривающие глубокое изучение индивидуальных способностей и потребностей каждого отдельного исполнителя с целью активизации его деятельности по достижению целей организации. Исследованы такие пути стимулирования сотрудников правоохранительной сферы, как участие в разработке и принятии решений, введение конкурсного получения вакантных должностей, демилитаризация специальных званий, демократизация кадровой политики, развитие профессиональной мобильности служащих.

Ключевые слова: мотивация, инновации, стимулирование, управление, реформирование, правоохранительная сфера, полиция, кадровая политика, международный опыт, европейские стандарты, международные эксперты.

Introduction. Today, the process of democratic transformation in our country related to the solution of complex political, economic, social and legal problems. One of the main problems is the reorganization of the government and the optimization of the structure of the institutions that represent it. Modern law enforcement sphere in its organization and activities are not fully compliant with the socio-political and criminal situation in the country. Since 2014 began the process of reforming the judicial system in accordance with social needs and possibilities of the state. Parliament adopted a new Law of Ukraine «On the national police» is considered the bill of the Ministry of Interior. This was an important proof of the reforms in the country [1].

Parliament adopted the documents were analyzed by international experts who provided comments of the Directorate General of Human Rights and Rule of Law Council of Europe [2; 3].

International experts have noted that Ukraine, as a member state of the Council of Europe, is obliged to improve their laws in line with European standards and use the innovative approaches at the decision of problems.

Statement of the problem. Study of the characteristics of management in the field of law enforcement of the state devoted to the works of famous scientists N. Andreev, V. Korobov, O. Bogutskaya, K. Kapustyanina, O. Klimenyuka, M. Pahulyuka, L. Nikiforova, O. Potemkin, M. Pogorelov, A. Gordienko and others [1–12]. However, improving the motivation system of law enforcement during the reform of the state apparatus has been insufficiently studied.

The objective of the study has to analyze the ways to build an effective system of motivation of workers during the restructuring of law enforcement sphere of the state. Explore the important areas of improving the motivations of social actors in the activities to achieve the strategic objectives in the struggle against crime, providing social security in all spheres of society.

Scientific problems have been solved by means of complex the scientific methods, analysis, synthesis and statistical comparisons. In the process of preparation and conduct of the study were used the following sources of information: educational and scientific materials, regulations, scientific and popular publications, official information in electronic databases of the Internet.

Results. Management law enforcement will be effective if the execution orders will be organized properly. Contractor should be clear to its purpose, and its actions must be motivated enough. Russian Empress Catherine II the question of why the nobility always fulfills its orders, replied: «Because I command them what they want» [4, p. 83].

So, the problem of motivation of the personnel of law enforcement agencies is the need to protection of society against crime should be transformed at policemen into own needs.

The main indicator of effective management of law enforcement in favor of a reaction to the changes taking place in the state, level and structure of crime. «The best structure is the one that allows the organization to more effectively interact with the environment, efficiently allocate and direct the efforts of their employees and, as a result, to meet the needs of the population in full» [5, p. 234].

At the moment when the law enforcement system is in crisis, it is especially important. Today, all the conditions for the adoption of innovative solutions to the development and implementation of a new law enforcement strategy. There is a need in the development of the law enforcement system, when the population feels the press of injustice and vulnerability to the crime and corruption.

To solve the problem of professional training, scientific and technical equipment of law enforcement agencies have the resources. This is – the accumulation of finances. Have a warranty of the law enforcement system. This is - the desire and the will of the country's leadership to change a situation in law enforcement. At the same time there is a significant disadvantage. At the same time there is a significant disadvantage. Managers and executives in the law enforcement agencies do not have the motivation of conscientious performance of professional duties [6, p. 78].

To develop innovative methods to solve the problem you need to understand that the motivation in the management of law enforcement is the process of prompting social entities to achieve the strategic objectives in the fight against crime and to provide social security to the material and spiritual spheres of society. At the same time, the motivation should not be confused with stimulation. Stimulation involves external - moral, physical, material impact on executors in order to strengthen their professional activities and direct impact on its results.

Motivation is a broader concept. On the one hand, this is the psychological process that begins with the physiological or psychological need that activates behavior creates a motivation to achieve the objective in professional activities. On the other, the manager must create conditions that motivate to work effectively, taking into account the material needs of individual performers or professional groups, their psychology and behavior.

For creation of an effective mechanism of motivation of law enforcement need to carefully study the needs of the staff. For example, according to the theory of hierarchy of needs of American psychologist Abraham Maslow, the founder of the «humanistic psychology», they form a structure of five types, largely determining human behavior. He highlighted the primary (physiological) needs for security, safety and secondary (social) needs of belonging to a social group (in particular the professional staff) in respect, self-expression and development [7, p. 119].

For example, the needs of poorly motivated professional activity of employees of law-enforcement sphere, if the primary and secondary rows needs are not satisfied. Some members of law enforcement agencies during the period of political and socio-economic reforms because of the unmet physical and social needs left the system; some were on the side of the criminals. Professional potential of employees greatly reduced.

According to current research needs and mechanisms to meet them operate in parallel. From this, scientists make an important conclusion about what needs the same level by means of a different level is impossible. It determines the need for greater attention to non-financial incentives in order to meet labor and the development of secondary human needs and, consequently, increase job satisfaction.

The law enforcement agencies have traditionally viewed motivation of activity from the perspective of achieved results, as a means of efficient operation. The focus is on increasing the salaries of employees, which, of course, necessary.

However, in the transition to a new model of law enforcement spheres of society, there is a need for new principles of organization of incentive system that will allow employees to not only decent wages, housing and medical care, but also the satisfaction of the work itself. Expectations of employees will be implemented if the necessary conditions for the professional development and development of creative abilities will be established [4, p. 174].

Thus, an innovative method of motivation is to create opportunities for more comprehensive realization of the individual abilities of employees. According to social psychologists, is the best form of social motivation. It involves deep study of individual abilities and needs of each individual performer for activation its actions to achieve objectives of the organization [8, p. 159]. And only at realization of this principle will be to achieve a new level of effectiveness of law enforcement.

An innovative solution to increase the efficiency of the Manager may be considered the search for ways to enhance its abilities to stimulate the participation of employees in development and decision-making. It greatly improves the intellectual potential of the whole law enforcement system and at the same time satisfies a deep need for self-expression and recognition of results of employees.

Employees of the new patrol police initially have motivation other than that which we inherited from the former Soviet more time. They will try to carefully carry out their duties. People who have graduated from a police school of a new type shall have a period of professional adaptation, time on skills practice. The process of improving the police will be long because the changed principles of motivation. The police now will not engage in corrupt acts, and would be willing to move up the career ladder, getting a decent social protection.

One of the most important motivational factors in the new police force will be higher wages. Of the candidates who have passed the professional psychological selection, we were selected workers who really like to defend and protect people. Of course, they will need a motivational support, at which will not have thoughts about how to support his family. When the policeman risks his life and protects people, and was waiting for him at home a hungry child, there is a situation in which it is at best simply will leave from the service, at worst – will be part of the corruption scheme [9, p. 94].

One of the important innovations in motivating of employees can be considered a creation of conditions for fair and objective competition at distribution of vacant posts. The motto of this method should be the slogan: «The competition from soldier to general» [5, p. 239]. International experts focused their attention on the appointment without competition for the top positions in the police force under the new law. The article 52 of the Law of Ukraine «On the national police» determined that the competition must be conducted only junior staff among those who first received the service [1].

Government Development Strategy of Internal Affairs and the coalition agreement of the parliamentary factions in 2014 provided for the use of competitive selection for all positions in the police, including top management [2].

Besides, according to international experts, the system of motivation of employees should be excluded component such as the preservation of militaristic special ranks, because it differs from the European practice of formation of a civil nature of the police service. The tendency of «militarization» of the police is not democratic practice and, therefore, the international experts condemn it.

For example, in Spain and France for police use such titles as «agent», «inspector», «commissar» and «the chief commissar» in Denmark for police use such titles as «assistant of police» and «the vice inspector of police». In Germany for police use such titles as the «master of police», «commissar of police», «the chief commissar of police» and «counsellor of police» [1].

Experts advise Ukrainian police take a similar system of special titles. Policemen are ordinary civil officials who are entitled to use of arms and other special means of limiting freedom of criminals. However, they are not military. In this case we are talking about changing the essence of motivation, since it is necessary to change not only the name of the titles officials as an approach to understanding the functions and objectives of the police in a democratic society.

Also, foreign researchers have made the remark that the «excessive powers» of the president to appoint the higher ranks of the top management of the police there is a serious demotivator law enforcement in Ukraine. According to experts, the head of state as the supreme commander of the Army of Ukraine should not have an impact on personnel politics in the police, which is the civil structure of the state.

Another innovative area of motivation of law enforcement can be considered the development of professional mobility of employees (movement of personnel, both horizontally and vertically, career development and promotion, training in various positions, the combination of professions, professional development). Today, the need to change the traditional negative attitude to the high mobility of staff law enforcement becomes important. Soviet personnel work was based on the opposite postulate: «Improvement works by reducing rotation of personnel» [11, p. 105].

Professional mobility helps employees to find effective ways of self-realization and to quickly adapt to changing conditions. It helps disseminate innovation and forms the basis for the preparation of the universal professionals who are capable of solving the problem of any complexity, including in law enforcement.

Conclusion. Thus, the innovative method to motivate the employees of law enforcement is not only in the creation of material conditions that will not only be appropriately level of professional risk wages, decent housing and health services, but also receive moral satisfaction from the work itself. Management of law enforcement agencies will be more effective if all the expectations of employees will be carried out will be created necessary conditions for the professional development and development of creative skills.

The novelty of the study is that analyzes the use of innovative methods of motivation for employees of law enforcement sphere in the period of radical reformation of society in Ukraine. The planned proposals designed to meet international standards of policing, including European ones.

The practical result is a complex study of the mechanism of reforming the law enforcement institutions of state and recommendations for the improvement of the new structure, which provides services for the protection of public order.

Further research in this field will contribute to the search for innovative ways to solve problems of reforming the law-enforcement sphere of our state.

Bibliographic references

1. Закон о полиции: замечания экспертов ЕС [Электронный ресурс]. – Режим доступа: <http://news.liga.net/news/politics/> (дата обращения 01.11.2015 г.). – Загл. с экрана.
2. Новая полиция: проблемы мотивации [Электронный ресурс]. – Режим доступа: <http://dumskaya.net/news/prisyagu> (дата обращения 01.11.2015 г.). – Загл. с экрана.
3. Проблеми мотивації [Електронний ресурс]. – Режим доступу: <http://www.esc.lviv.ua/problemy-motyvatiji/> (дата звернення 01.11.2015 р.). – Заголовок з екрана.
4. **Андреев, Н. А.** Стратегическое управление в правоохранительной сфере [Текст] / Н. А. Андреев, В. Б. Коробов. – М.: ЮНИТИ-ДАНА, 2012. – 359 с.
5. **Клименюк, О. М.** Удосконалення механізму державного управління правоохоронною діяльністю [Текст] / О. М. Клименюк // АМУУ. – 2012. – С. 231–239.
6. **Бугуцький, О. А.** Фактори розвитку мотивації праці [Текст] / О. А. Бугуцький // Економіка АПК. – 2014. – № 7. – С. 78–79.
7. **Дворецька, Г. В.** Ставлення до праці і проблеми мотивації трудової діяльності [Текст]: навч. посіб. / Г. В. Дворецька. – К.: КНЕУ, 2012. – 214 с.
8. **Капустянин, К. О.** Формування цілісної системи мотивації персоналу [Текст] / К. О. Капустянин // Економіка та підприємництво. – 2012. – №1. – С. 159–164.
9. **Пахулюк, М. О.** Проблеми мотивації праці [Текст] / М. О. Пахулюк, Л. О. Нікіфорова // Пробл. економіки ХХІ ст. – 2010. – №3. – С. 94.
10. **Потьомкіна, О. В.** Системний підхід у мотивації працівників банківської сфери [Текст] / О. В. Потьомкіна // Екон. форум. – 2011. – №1. – С. 125.
11. **Погорєлов, М. І.** Сучасні проблеми мотивації працівників [Текст] / М. І. Погорєлов, А. Д. Гордієнко // Вісн. НТУ «ХП». – 2013. – № 22. – С. 105–109.
12. **Степаненко, Ж.** Проблеми мотивації персоналу [Електронний ресурс] / Ж. Степаненко. – Режим доступу: <http://oldconf.neasmo.org.ua/node/3159> (дата звернення 01.11.2015 р.). – Заголовок з екрана.

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ПРОФЕСІЙНА КУЛЬТУРА І БЕЗПЕКА: ІННОВАЦІЙНИЙ ПІДХІД ДО ВПРОВАДЖЕННЯ В МЕДИЧНОМУ ЗАКЛАДІ

Запропоновано окремі підходи до трактування сутності, видів і складових елементів культури безпеки (КБ) в організації; надано можливий метод оцінки; сформульовано поняття професійної культури безпеки з урахуванням особливостей медичної галузі; запропоновано